

A REVIEW OF TIROFIBAN'S SAFETY AND EFFICACY IN THE MANAGEMENT OF STROKE: CURRENT INSIGHTS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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ABSTRACT

Stroke is a leading cause of mortality and morbidity worldwide, necessitating the continuous exploration of novel therapeutic interventions to improve patient outcomes. One such intervention under investigation is the use of tirofiban, a glycoprotein IIb/IIIa receptor antagonist commonly used in the management of acute coronary syndromes. Preclinical studies have demonstrated the potential neuroprotective effects of tirofiban, including the inhibition of platelet aggregation, reduction of inflammation, and improvement of microcirculation. Clinical trials evaluating tirofiban in acute ischemic stroke have reported conflicting findings regarding its efficacy in improving functional outcomes and reducing mortality. Some studies

have demonstrated potential benefits in terms of recanalization rates, reduced infarct size, and improved neurological recovery, while others have failed to show significant clinical improvements. The optimal dosing regimen, timing of administration, and patient selection criteria remain areas of ongoing investigation and debate. Safety considerations of tirofiban include the risk of bleeding complications, particularly in combination with thrombolytic therapy. Adverse events, such as major hemorrhage or allergic reactions, should be carefully monitored. Risk stratification, appropriate patient selection, and individualized treatment plans are crucial factors to optimize the benefit-risk profile of tirofiban in stroke patients. Tirofiban holds promise as a therapeutic option for stroke management, particularly in ischemic stroke. Further investigation, including larger randomized controlled trials, is

necessary to establish the optimal use, dosing, and patient selection criteria for tirofiban in stroke.

KEYWORDS: Tirofiban, endovascular treatment, Recanalization, Functional outcome.

INTRODUCTION

Ischemic stroke is the most common cerebrovascular accident accounting for approximately 87% of all strokes due to disruption of blood flow in the brain.^[1] Acute occlusion of the cerebral artery leads to time-dependent ischemic brain tissue damage. One of the primary causes of disability and mortality worldwide is acute ischemic stroke (AIS).^[2]

Patients with AIS typically receive intravenous thrombolysis or/and intra-arterial thrombectomy to unblock blocked cerebral arteries. Evidence exists that endovascular treatment (EVT) dramatically increases the rate of recanalization and improves the functional outcomes of patients with acute ischemic stroke due to large vessel occlusion compared to thrombolysis.^[3] There are several EVT strategies, such as mechanical thrombectomy, angioplasty, and stenting. Each strategy has a specific group of AIS patients.^[1] However, endovascular thrombectomy has been unsuccessful in producing successful reperfusion in approximately 30% of patients.^[4]

Moreover, endovascular therapy can only be carried out at selected high-performing stroke facilities. Intravenous thrombolysis with recombinant tissue plasminogen activator is still the cornerstone of care for AIS patients in smaller facilities.^[3]

Early neurological deterioration (END) within the first 24 hours following intravenous thrombolysis is a significant concern that results in poor outcomes in AIS patients. The pathogenic mechanisms at the root of END are widely unknown and exact medical treatment that prevent or reverse END are lacking.^[3] The symptoms of neurological deficits after the onset of ischemic stroke in progressive ischemic stroke (PIS) are mild but progressive.^[5]

Tirofiban is a highly selective nonpeptide platelet glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitor.^[4] It prevents fibrinogen from binding to glycoprotein IIb/IIIa and blocks the final common pathway of platelet aggregation. It has a shorter half-life of 1.5-2 hours. Following cessation of tirofiban administration, platelet aggregation recovers to 50% of the baseline within 4 hours.^[3] Tirofiban has been approved by the US Food and Drug Administration for the treatment of acute coronary syndrome but not yet for AIS.^[1] Currently, the application of tirofiban in acute

ischemic stroke has been investigated in number of studies, and tirofiban is thought to rapidly inhibit platelet aggregation, dissolve micro-thrombi and increase the rate of vascular recanalization.^[5]

OBJECTIVE

This review aims to provide an overview of the existing literature on the subject, assessing the safety and efficacy of tirofiban in stroke patients.

MECHANISM OF ACTION

Tirofiban is a highly selective, reversible, competitive, nonpeptide platelet glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitor. It exerts its effects via the prevention of the binding of fibrinogen and other ligands, resulting in the inhibition of the last common step of thrombi formation.

AN OVERVIEW ON TIROFIBAN IN CLINICAL PRACTICE

Indications and usage

Tirofiban is suggested in individuals with non-ST elevation acute coronary syndrome to minimize the risk of thrombotic cardiovascular events (combined endpoint of mortality, myocardial infarction, or refractory ischemia/repeat cardiac operation).

Dosage and administration

Administer intravenously 25 mcg/kg within 5 minutes and then 0.15 mcg/kg/min (or 0.075 mcg/kg/min for patients with serum creatinine ≤ 60 mL/min), for up to 18 hours.

Dosage forms and strengths

Premixed 5 mg tirofiban per 100 mL (50 mcg per mL) and 12.5 mg tirofiban per 250 mL (50 mcg per mL) are clear, non-preserved, sterile solutions premixed in a vehicle made isotonic with sodium chloride.

Contraindications

- In patients with severe hypersensitivity reaction
- In patients with a history of thrombocytopenia following prior exposure to tirofiban
- Active internal bleeding or a history of bleeding diathesis, major surgical procedure, or severe physical trauma within the previous month.

Warnings and precautions

- **Bleeding:-** Bleeding is the most common complication encountered during therapy with Tirofiban. Bleeding commonly associated with the use of tirofiban usually occurs at the arterial access site during cardiac catheterization. To minimize the risk of bleeding, it is recommended to avoid or limit the use of procedures that could potentially cause trauma, such as arterial and venous punctures, intramuscular injections, and nasotracheal intubation. Additionally, the collateral use of fibrinolytic, oral anticoagulants, and other antiplatelet drugs can increase the risk of bleeding and should be used with caution.
- **Thrombocytopenia:-** Profound thrombocytopenia has been reported with tirofiban. Monitor platelet counts beginning about 6 hours after treatment initiation and daily thereafter. If the platelet count decreases to $<90,000/\text{mm}^3$, monitor platelet counts to exclude pseudo thrombocytopenia. If thrombocytopenia is confirmed, discontinue Tirofiban and heparin. Previous exposure to a glycoprotein (GP) IIb/IIIa receptor antagonist may increase the risk of developing thrombocytopenia.

Adverse effects

>10%

Bleeding, minor (11%)

1-10%

Pelvic pain (6%)

Coronary artery dissection (5%)

Bradycardia (4%)

Dizziness (3%)

Lower extremity pain (3%)

Edema (2%)

Sweating (2%)

Bleeding, major (1-2%)

Thrombocytopenia (1.5%)

Drug interactions

Some of the drugs that can interact with tirofiban include:

- ❖ Anticoagulants: Such as heparin or warfarin - may increase the risk of bleeding.
- ❖ Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) - such as aspirin, ibuprofen, or naproxen - may also increase the risk of bleeding.
- ❖ Thrombolytic agents: Such as alteplase - may increase the risk of bleeding.
- ❖ Other platelet inhibitors: Such as clopidogrel, prasugrel, or ticagrelor - may also increase the risk of bleeding.

Use in specific populations

Pregnancy

Category B- There is a lack of sufficient and reliable studies in pregnant women to evaluate the safety and effectiveness of using tirofiban during pregnancy. However, studies conducted on pregnant rats and rabbits have shown that tirofiban is able to cross the placenta. In these animal studies, intravenous doses of tirofiban HCl up to 5 mg/kg/day were administered, which is approximately 5 and 13 times higher than the maximum recommended daily human dose for rats and rabbits, respectively, when compared on a body surface area basis. These studies did not reveal any harm to the developing fetus.

Nursing Mothers- The extent to which tirofiban is excreted in human milk is currently unknown. However, studies have shown that significant levels of tirofiban are present in the milk of lactating rats. Since many drugs are known to be excreted in human milk and could potentially cause harm to nursing infants, it is recommended to either discontinue nursing or discontinue the use of tirofiban, taking into consideration the potential risks and benefits for both the mother and infant

Pediatric- Safety and effectiveness in pediatric patients have not been established.

Geriatric- No dosage adjustment is recommended for elderly population.

Renal Insufficiency- Patients with moderate to severe renal insufficiency have decreased plasma clearance of Tirofiban. Reduce the dosage of Tirofiban in patients with severe renal insufficiency.

OUTCOME MEASURE

The 2 primary safety outcome endpoints include symptomatic intracranial hemorrhage(sICH) and mortality.

The 2 efficacy outcome endpoints include recanalization rate and favorable functional outcome.

Table 2: Safety and efficacy of Tirofiban in stroke.

Authors	Study	Results
RESCUE BT Trial Investigators et al AUG-22	Effect of Intravenous Tirofiban vs Placebo Before Endovascular Thrombectomy on Functional Outcomes in Large Vessel Occlusion Stroke	The results do not support the use of intravenous tirofiban prior to endovascular thrombectomy for acute ischemic stroke.
N. DU, L.-X. WANG, Y.-L. LIU, X.-L. YIN, J.-S. ZHAO, L. YANG MARCH-22	Effect of tirofiban in treating patients with progressive ischemic stroke (PIS)	Tirofiban combined with conventional basic therapy can greatly enhance neurological deficits and the outcome of the disease, and reduce platelet adhesion and activation without enhancing the risk of hemorrhage in PIS patients
Yan Zhang et al OCT-22	Prospective pilot study of tirofiban in progressive stroke after intravenous thrombolysis	Early low-dose therapy of tirofiban in AIS patients with neurologic deterioration following intra-vascular thrombectomy potentially enhanced functional recovery and alleviated neurologic deficits as early as 7 days and did not increase the risk of various hemorrhagic complications.
Bin Han et al FEB-22	Efficacy and Safety of Tirofiban in Clinical Patients With Acute Ischemic Stroke	This study claims that tirofiban was safe and effective and could be a remedial treatment for patients with AIS who have not been recanalized.
Tang L. ·Tang X. · Yang Q JAN-21	The Application of Tirofiban in the Endovascular Treatment of Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Meta-Analysis	The application of tirofiban in EVT of AIS may enhance functional outcomes and lower the rates of mortality at 3 months.
Chunrong Tao et al JUN-21	Association between tirofiban monotherapy and efficacy and	This study suggests that the use of tirofiban as monotherapy appears to be

	safety in acute ischemic stroke	safe in AIS treatment in comparison with routine dual antiplatelet therapy, however, no improvement in functional performance was identified.
Yongdong Sun et al NOV-21	Effect of Tirofiban on new cerebral microbleeds after mechanical thrombectomy in patients with acute ischemic stroke	The application of tirofiban in patients of mechanical thrombectomy with acute ischemic stroke has better safety, effectively alleviates the occurrence of new cerebral microhemorrhage, and gives a guarantee for patient safety.
Hongchen Zhao et al FEB-21	Sequential tirofiban infusions combined with endovascular treatment may improve outcomes in acute ischemic stroke - a meta-analysis	Loading dose of tirofiban followed by low-dose maintenance may enhance functional outcomes of endovascular therapy in acute ischemic stroke.
Lihua Zhu et al AUG-21	Safety and efficacy of intravenous Tirofiban infusion after mechanical thrombectomy in acute ischemic stroke: a retrospective observational study	Intravenous Tirofiban infusion after mechanical thrombectomy is safe and effective in patients with acute ischemic stroke.
Goating Ma et al JUN-21	Safety and Efficacy of Low-Dose Tirofiban Combined With Intravenous Thrombolysis and Mechanical Thrombectomy in Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Matched-Control Analysis From a Nationwide Registry	Patients with acute ischemic stroke who underwent mechanical thrombectomy and preceding intravenous thrombolysis, low-dose tirofiban was not associated with an increased risk of sICH or ICH..
Zhiyong Fu et al JUL-20	Safety and Efficacy of Tirofiban in Acute Ischemic Stroke Patients Receiving Endovascular Treatment: A Meta-Analysis	Tirofiban is safe in AIS patients with ET and can significantly reduce mortality; preoperative tirofiban may be effective, but further studies are needed to confirm its efficacy.
Lili Zhao et al. APRIL-20	The Safety and Efficiency of Tirofiban in Acute Ischemic Stroke Patients Treated with Mechanical Thrombectomy: A Multicenter Retrospective Cohort Study	Tirofiban may help AIS patients given MT to gain functional independence faster, without increasing the risk of complications
J Zhou et al FEB-20	Safety and efficacy of tirofiban in acute ischemic stroke patients not receiving endovascular treatment: a systematic review and meta-analysis	Tirofiban appears to be safe when used following IV thrombolysis or as monotherapy in AIS patients. Conclusions regarding improvement in functional improvement cannot be drawn. Further trials are needed to strengthen the evidence on this topic
Zhe Cheng et al OCT-19	Intravenous Administration of Standard Dose Tirofiban after Mechanical Arterial Recanalization is Safe and Relatively Effective in Acute	The intravenous application of a standard dose of tirofiban post-Solitair stent retriever thrombectomy and intravenous thrombolysis appears to be safe and relatively effective in acute

	Ischemic Stroke	ischemic stroke.
Jin Liu et al APRIL-19	Efficacy of Tirofiban Administered at Different Time Points after Intravenous Thrombolytic Therapy with Alteplase in Patients with Acute Ischemic Stroke	Tirofiban combined with alteplase is effective and safe, and particularly beneficial when administered at 2 hour and 2-12 hours after intravenous thrombolysis with alteplase in acute ischemic stroke.
Zhao et al NOV-2017	Low-dose tirofiban improves functional outcome in acute ischemic stroke patients treated with endovascular thrombectomy	In patients with AIS undergoing ET, tirofiban is not associated with higher sICH, it seems to lead to lower odds of deaths and better odds of long-term functional independence

Efficacy of Tirofiban in Stroke

Several studies have investigated the efficacy of tirofiban in acute ischemic stroke. While the results are mixed, there is some evidence to suggest that tirofiban may be beneficial in certain patient populations.

1. **Improvement in Recanalization:** Some studies have reported improved recanalization rates with the use of tirofiban in combination with other treatments such as tPA or mechanical thrombectomy. This suggests that tirofiban may help facilitate the restoration of blood flow in occluded vessels, potentially improving outcomes.
2. **Reduction in Secondary Infarction:** Tirofiban's antiplatelet properties may reduce the risk of secondary infarction by preventing the formation of new clots in the affected vessels. This could lead to a reduction in the size of the infarct and better functional outcomes.
3. **Neurological Improvement:** Some studies have reported improved neurological outcomes in patients treated with tirofiban, including a reduction in the severity of neurological deficits and improved functional independence.

Safety of Tirofiban in Stroke

The safety profile of tirofiban in stroke patients is an important consideration. Like any medication, tirofiban is associated with potential risks and adverse effects. In the context of stroke, bleeding is of particular concern, as it can exacerbate the neurological injury.

CONCLUSION

In patients with acute myocardial infarction, GP IIb/IIIa receptor antagonist has been extensively used to prevent platelet aggregation and thrombosis. Not only does tirofiban inhibit platelet aggregation, but it also inhibits the inflammatory response and reduces reperfusion injury by inhibiting the expression of inflammatory factors, which can also be the

reason for enhancing the functional outcomes of AIS patients. While due to its potential for hemorrhagic transformation, its application in stroke is limited.

The efficacy of tirofiban on the forecast in Acute ischemic stroke patients undergoing mechanical thrombectomy remains disputable. Collaboration between stroke specialists, neurologists, and interventional radiologists is crucial to determine the most appropriate approach for each patient. However, further studies are required to determine the optimal patient inclusion criteria, dose of tirofiban, and the methods to establish a standard treatment protocol.

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